

Use of Electric Vehicles in Sustainable Urban Logistics

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ABSTRACT

Sustainable urban logistics is gaining increasing importance in terms of reducing environmental impacts and improving quality of life. The widespread adoption of electric vehicles has emerged as a key component of this process. This study conducts a bibliometric analysis of academic publications from the past decade that focus on the use of electric vehicles and charging infrastructure in sustainable urban logistics. A total of 1,082 articles obtained from the Web of Science and Scopus databases were analyzed using co-word, citation, and co-citation methods with the help of VOSviewer and BibExcel software. The findings reveal that China and the United States are the leading countries in terms of publication output in this field, and the most contributing journals are published by IEEE and Elsevier. By uncovering the structure and trends of scientific production on sustainable urban logistics and the integration of electric vehicles, this research provides valuable insights for policymakers, local governments, and the academic community.

Keywords: *Urban logistics, Electric vehicles, Sustainability, Charging infrastructure, Bibliometric analysis*

1. INTRODUCTION

In the second quarter of the 21st century, increasing urbanization rates, deepening environmental sustainability concerns, and transportation-related carbon emissions reaching critical levels have necessitated the redesign of urban logistics systems. At the heart of this transformation are electric vehicles (EVs), which are expected to replace fossil fuel-based transportation vehicles. Initially emerging as a trend towards environmentally friendly alternatives for individual users, EV technology has now become central to the logistics sector, becoming a decisive factor in terms of both operational efficiency and social responsibility, particularly in urban transportation.

The impact of freight vehicles on CO₂ and other air pollutant emissions in urban areas has been extensively studied in the literature. Although light commercial vehicles and trucks account for 10–15% of urban vehicle kilometers traveled, they are responsible for up to one-third of total traffic-related emissions (Zhao et al., 2023). In this context, the goal is to transform urban freight transport into a more environmentally friendly and carbon-neutral structure (Chaiyakan, 2016). Considering the volumes of freight transported and the distances involved, electrification of existing vehicles is considered the most viable solution (Napoli et al., 2021). However, the penetration of electric vehicles is still limited; high costs, operational limitations, and a lack of commitment to change are contributing factors (Wang and Thoben, 2016).

In major metropolises like Istanbul and throughout Turkey, urban logistics plays a crucial role in economic and environmental sustainability (Imre et al., 2023). Türkiye's exports to European Union countries and the environmental agreements it is a party to (such as the Kyoto Protocol, the Paris Agreement, and the Green Deal) further necessitate this transformation process. The role of electric vehicles is critical in restructuring urban logistics in line with sustainability, livability, and resilience goals (Taefi et al., 2015). The study's fundamental assumptions are as follows:

- Electric vehicle adoption will exceed 50% in the next 10 years.

- Total ownership costs will equal those of conventional vehicles (Quak and Nesterova, 2018).
- Society's perspective on electric vehicles will become more positive.
- The development of charging infrastructure will enable uninterrupted logistics operations (Hogt et al., 2017).

While numerous publications on sustainable urban logistics and electric vehicles exist in the literature, bibliometric studies that systematically visualize and analyze trends in this area are quite limited (Catta et al., 2005). This study conducts a bibliometric analysis of 1082 articles published in the Web of Science and Scopus databases between 2014 and 2024, mapping the developments, researchers, journals, and countries in this field. This study aims to contribute to practitioners and policymakers by presenting scientific knowledge and trends in the field.

The main research question can be summarized as follows:

“What are the key components influencing the use of electric vehicles in sustainable urban logistics?”

The following sub-questions are also addressed within this framework:

1. What is the overview presented in the literature?
2. What is the development trajectory of electric vehicles and charging stations?
3. What are the most current research topics in the field?
4. Which authors, countries, and journals are at the forefront?

This study aims to evaluate the scientific basis for the sustainability and electrification-based transformation in urban logistics using findings obtained from large datasets.

The impact of freight vehicles on CO₂ and other air pollutant emissions in urban areas is widely studied. While light commercial vehicles and trucks account for 10–15% of urban

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2. METHODOLOGY

In this study, the bibliometric method was used to analyze the literature on the use of electric vehicles in sustainable urban logistics. Bibliometric methods are used for various reasons, including investigating article and journal performance, collaboration models, trends in research components, and the intellectual structure of a scientific field. This method, which allows for the meticulous interpretation of large volumes of unstructured data, reveals the cumulative scientific knowledge of the research field and contributes to the identification of knowledge gaps (Öztürk, 2021).

In this context, the data source for this study consists of scientific articles published in the Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus databases between 2014 and 2024. Bibliographic data was taken from these two databases together and integrated for analysis. While WoS stands out for its extensive data coverage and high representation of English-language journals, especially in Western languages, Scopus was chosen due to its broader publication coverage and superiority in non-English publications. Both databases are considered to have complementary characteristics.

The dataset consists of 1082 articles covering the themes of sustainable urban logistics, electric vehicles, charging stations, and environmental sustainability. Only research and review articles published in peer-reviewed journals were included in the study. Book chapters, proceedings, conference papers, and other documents not subject to peer review were excluded. Furthermore, articles that did not include the study's focal concepts (urban logistics, electric vehicles, charging stations, sustainability) in their titles, abstracts, or keywords were excluded. Duplicate records in WoS and Scopus were eliminated, and the remaining articles were manually evaluated for relevance.

VOSviewer and BibExcel software were used during the data analysis process. These software programs conducted keyword matching, citation analysis, co-citation analysis, and bibliographic matching. The primary objective of the analyses was to reveal the intellectual structure, conceptual clusters, and development trends of publications in the research field. The co-word analysis evaluated the co-occurrence of concepts derived from the articles' titles, abstracts, and keywords. Data obtained using BibExcel was imported into VOSviewer software, and network visualization was performed.

This study combines performance analysis and scientific mapping methods. Performance analysis focuses on numerical outputs such as the distribution of publications by year and the productivity of authors, countries, institutions, and journals, while scientific mapping evaluates the relationships between these components at a conceptual level.

Based on the collected data, bibliometric analysis revealed the field's scientific orientation, prominent actors, development trends, and conceptual clusters.

3. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1. Document Type and the Books

After applying the inclusion principles, the findings revealed that 99.81% of the 1,082 articles were research articles (Table 1). These figures demonstrate that researchers prioritize empirical studies. As seen in Figure 1 below, the number of studies has been steadily increasing between 2014 and 2024.

The books published in this study are mostly related to engineering, transportation power systems, mobility, and sustainability. No more than three publications were published on the same topic (Table 2).

Table 1. Types of documents related to research

Document Type	Record	Percentage % (Total = 1,082 records)
Article	1,080	99.81%
Book Chapters	14	1.24%
Editorial Material	1	0.09%
Othes	1	0.09%

Table 2. Recorded Books

Topics of the books	Record	Percentage
Artech House Power Engineering Series	3	%0.277
Iet Energy Engineering	1	%0.092
Iet Transportation Series	3	%0.277

3.2. Findings from the articles

Electrification is the most frequently published topic in journals, and in our article, electric vehicles interact most closely with charging stations. Energy, transportation, and the environment have been the most advanced topics studied. The distribution of the 1,082 articles is as shown in the accompanying table, with Elsevier and IEEE publishing more

than half of the articles. The most relevant sources for electric vehicles in sustainable urban logistics are IEEE (Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers), the institution that has conducted the most comprehensive research on electrification and the institution that has published the most. Elsevier appears to have produced the most comprehensive and noteworthy studies on urban logistics and electric vehicles.

Figure 1. Citations and distribution of publications by year (WoS, 2025)

Table 3. The top 15 publishing houses with the most publications

Publisher	Quant.	Publication	Quant.
Elsevier	495	SAGE Publications	76
Springer Nature	280	Public Library of Science (PLoS)	58
Taylor & Francis	176	Oxford University Press (OUP)	55
MDPI	152	Hindawi	54
Wiley	147	Cambridge University Press (CUP)	51

IEEE	145	American Society of Civil Engineers (ASCE)	47
Informa UK Limited	105	Emerald	36
Wolters Kluwer Health	83		

(WoS, 2025)

English, with 1065 publications, constitutes a significant portion of the publications. Polish follows with 10 publications and German with 6 publications.

Table 4. Article Languages

Languagee	Records	% in 1,082
English	1,065	98.42%
German	6	0.55%
Dialect	10	0.92%
Slovenian	1	0.09%

(WoS, 2025)

Chinese researchers led the way with 375 publications, while the number of American researchers was 242, Indian researchers 138, and Turkish researchers 8 (Figure 2).

As seen in Table 5, the publications' fields of interest, particularly those related to electrical and electronics engineering, are particularly prominent, reflecting the technical nature of the topic. Articles on urban logistics, transportation, and environmental sustainability are particularly prevalent. A detailed distribution of topics is listed in Table5.

Figure 2. Countries of researchers conducting research (WoS, 2025)

Table 5. Enrollment distribution table by scientific fields

Scientific Area	Number of Records	% Percentage
EEE	650	60.67%
Fuel Energy	254	23.67%
Lojistics Science and Tech.	234	21.83%
Transportation	121	11.29%
Environmenttal Science	98	9.14%
Urban Studies	4	0.37%
Public management	2	0.19%
Territory Urrban Olanning	1	0.09%

Table 6. Researched topics

Title/Topics	Recorded Numbers	% Percentage
Case Studies on Transport Policy	14	1.29%
Chemosphere	8	0.74%
Electric Power Components and Systems	20	1.85%
Electric Power Systems Research	56	5.18%
Electrical Engineering	20	1.85%
Energy Storage	9	0.83%
eTransportation	12	1.11%
IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics	31	2.87%
IEEE Transactions on Power Systems	34	3.14%
IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid	107	9.89%
IEEE Transactions on Transportation Electrification	65	6.01%
IET Electric Power Transmission Systems	24	2.22%
International Journal of Electric and Hybrid Vehicles	9	0.83%
International Journal of Electrical Power Energy Systems	67	6.19%
International Journal of Emerging Electric Power Systems	11	1.02%
International Journal of Renewable Energy Research	19	1.76%
Journal of Electrical Engineering Technology	10	0.92%
Journal of Energy Storage	106	9.80%
Przegląd Elektrotechniczny	16	1.48%
Science of the Total Environment	16	1.48%
Solar Energy	9	0.83%
Sustainable Energy Grids and Networks	53	4.90%
Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies	41	3.79%
Transportation Research Part D: Transport and Environment	80	7.39%

(WoS, 2025)

3.3. Findings According to the Authors

Our study includes articles by authors with multiple articles, and it is observed that Chinese authors have a higher number of articles and a higher number of articles. We observed that authors from different institutions in different countries have published multiple articles. Shahidehpour Mohammad ranked first with 20 articles, Hu Zechun 13, Yang Dong Zhao 10, Zhang Hongcai 10, and Shao Chengcheng 8.

Although the authors were from different countries, a significant portion of the publications were published in English. The articles were predominantly written by Chinese authors. 375 Chinese studies, 242 from the US, and 138 from India were the leading authors. Eight publications from Turkey were also criticized in these studies.

Table 7. Authors who did the most research

Authors	Recorded Number	% Percentage
Shahidehpour M	20	1.85%
Zhang HC	20	1.85%
Hu ZC	13	1.20%
Dong ZY	10	0.92%
Song YH	10	0.92%
Li Y	9	0.83%
Qiu J	9	0.83%
Singh H	8	0.74%
Li K	7	0.65%
Yu J	7	0.65%
Zhang J	7	0.65%
Zhang K	7	0.65%
Zhou Y	7	0.65%

(WoS, 2025)

3.4. Findings According to the Universities and Supporters

Of the 1,082 articles reviewed, Tsinghua University contributed the most with 25 articles, the University of Texas with 19 articles, and the University of Sydney with 18. Studies from Chinese and American universities are also prominent. An increase in publications on these topics has been observed in recent years at Indian universities. The accompanying table lists eight universities with a significant body of research in the field. While universities from these three countries have contributed the most to the fields of electric vehicles, environmental science, and transportation and logistics, all developed and developing countries have published at least some research on this topic. Yıldız Technical University and Eskişehir Technical University from Turkey were also among the universities contributing to these studies.

Table 8. Most Efficient Universities

University	Record	Percentage
Faculty of Electrical and Information Technology, University of Sydney	34	3.14%
Applied Electromagnetic Engineering and Technology Laboratory of Huazhong University of Science and Technology	30	2.77%
Department of Electrical Engineering, Tsinghua University	25	2.31%
Southeast University Electrical Engineering Department	20	1.85%
School of Electrical and Information Engineering, University of Sydney	14	1.29%
School of Engineering, Faculty of Science and Technology, Tsinghua University	11	1.02%
School of Electrical Engineering, University of New South Wales	8	0.74%

(WoS, 2025)

3.5. Scientific Area and Catgoric Studies

This section evaluates the interactions and structural connections between the components of electric vehicle use in sustainable urban logistics. The aim is to identify the most frequently used keywords in the most studied subtopics, as well as the most cited studies. Additionally, this analysis aims to reveal the networks of studies and journals in the field. Therefore, three different bibliometric methods were used in this section: co-word analysis, citation analysis, and co-citation analysis. Bibliometric studies typically employ analysis (classification) and visualization processes. Similarity matrices were calculated throughout the analysis, and the relationships between various elements, such as articles, authors, journals, and keywords, were examined. Researchers frequently use software tools such as Pajek, BibExcel, SciMat, and VOSviewer to perform these analyses. For this particular study, BibExcel and VOSviewer were used as bibliometric software tools.

Figure 3. Citation Analysis Heat/Density Map
(WoS, 2025)

3.5.1. Keyword Analysis

In keyword analysis, the unit of analysis is words, and in this analysis, the title, abstract, and keywords, concepts, and their relationships are examined (Ronda et al., 2012). A keyword analysis aims to find two keywords. It brings together keywords from different

Figures 4 and 5 show the frequency of keyword use across articles. Red areas in the figure represent the most frequently used words, yellow areas represent the less frequently used words. Green and blue areas represent the least frequently used words. The size of the letters within the figure corresponds to the frequency of each keyword.

The most frequently used keyword is "electric vehicle" with 76 occurrences. Following this, 'power charging' was used 28 times, and 'battery' was used 22 times. These keywords indicate recurring themes and concepts in the analyzed articles. The subheadings expressed here appear to be central concepts in the use of electric vehicles in sustainable urban logistics.

Figure 5. The most frequently cited keywords in the field of urban logistics electric vehicles, vehicle batteries and charging stations (Vosviewer, 2025)

3.5.2 Cite Analysis

Citation analysis provides information about the impact of studies and is based on the principle that authors' studies are cited by other researchers (Tavares-Lehmann and Varum, 2021; Ejsmont et al., 2020). This analysis recognizes a positive relationship between the number of citations and the impact of the cited study. It allows the identification of highly cited (or influential) studies, authors, or journals in the field (Öztürk, 2021). Consequently, citation analysis provides insight into the relative impact and importance of studies in a given research area. Studies with the highest impact in their

citations to be considered in the analysis. According to this criterion, a total of 176 journals were included after meeting the threshold. The journal-level co-citation analysis is shown in Figure 4. The analysis results show that, with a total of 1,357 joint citations, M. Elsevier and IEEE are the publishers that publish more than half of the articles. The most relevant sources for electric vehicles in sustainable urban logistics are IEEE (Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers), which has conducted the most comprehensive studies on electrification and has published the most. Elsevier appears to have produced the most comprehensive and noteworthy studies on urban logistics and electric vehicles.

The most productive journals in the field of urban logistics electric vehicles, vehicle batteries, and charging stations were evaluated for compliance with the Bradford Law. Bradford's Law, which ranks journals according to their productivity, helps identify the core journals in a given subject area. According to this law, journals are divided into three groups, each containing an equal number of articles.

Object: The first group consists of a small number of journals that cover only one-third of the total articles. These journals are considered core publications. The second group consists of a larger number of journals that publish the remaining one-third of all articles (Chen and Leimkuhler, 1986). Finally, the third group includes a significantly larger number of journals and accounts covering the remaining one-third of the articles. This study included 165 articles in the analysis, 11 of which are core journals, falling into the first region according to Bradford's law. The second region comprises 32 journals, and the third region comprises 125 journals.

Field: The total number of citations in the articles included in the analysis was 13,263. 6,465 of the total citations were to the most frequently cited core journals in the first region (Figure 5). Elsevier and IEEE were the publishers that published more than half of the articles. The most relevant sources for electric vehicles in sustainable urban logistics are IEEE (Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers), which has conducted the most comprehensive research on electrification and published the most. Elsevier appears to have produced the most comprehensive and significant work on urban logistics and electric vehicles.

The distribution of journals and citations complies with Bradford's law, indicating the existence of a core group of journals that can serve as a valuable reference point. Figure 5 highlights this core group of journals, which provide valuable insights into tracking developments and identifying gaps in research on electric vehicles in sustainable urban logistics. Researchers can gain valuable insights into the current state of the literature in this field by focusing on the core group of journals identified in Figure 5. These journals are likely to contain influential articles and provide a comprehensive overview of progress in electric vehicles research in sustainable urban logistics that warrants further research.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study analyzed 1082 articles published in 48 journals in the WoS and SCOPUS databases between 2014 and 2024, based on exclusion and inclusion criteria. The research focused on the key concepts of urban logistics, electric vehicles, environment, and sustainability, as well as the charging station and battery subcomponents. The aim was to reveal the trend of publications on the use of electric vehicles in sustainable urban logistics and the intellectual, social, and conceptual structure of the field.

The research findings indicate an increase in publications on electric vehicles and charging stations, particularly after 2017. A significant portion of the 1082 studies (85%) were produced after 2020. The proliferation of electric vehicles has progressed in parallel with countries' environmental and climate policies. The most frequently used keywords were electric vehicle, charging station, battery and environment. International regulations such as the Kyoto Protocol, the Paris Agreement, and the Green Deal have influenced policies regarding electric vehicles. These policies have increased electric vehicle sales while contributing to reducing environmental impacts. Furthermore, technological studies have accelerated to address technical barriers such as the development of charging station infrastructure and range/charging time.

The importance of electric vehicles in reducing environmental impacts and minimizing costs in last-mile logistics is emphasized. Increasing public awareness and consciousness

is also among the aims of the study. Future research could include databases such as Google Scholar, PubMed, and Dimensions for more comprehensive analyses. Furthermore, various software programs such as Citespace and Pajek could be used. The topic could also be further explored by exploring topics such as charging station distribution, battery technologies, renewable energy, and smart city technologies. This research contributes to scientific and applied studies by revealing the evolution of electric vehicle use in urban logistics.

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